

CHEMISTRY OF THE RARE-EARTHS. PART II. MACRO- AND MICRO-ESTIMATION OF CAESIUM IN PRESENCE OF POTASSIUM AND RUBIDIUM WITH THE HELP OF RARE-EARTHS

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An improved method for the quantitative determination of caesium and its separation from rubidium and potassium has been described. Cs has been precipitated as $Cs_2NaLa(NO_2)_6$ and weighed directly in a gooch crucible. Cs has also been determined volumetrically by estimating the nitrite content of the compound with ceric sulphate. Both gravimetric and volumetric processes have been successfully adopted for micro-determination of caesium.

The close similarity in the chemical behaviour of potassium, rubidium and caesium is well known. Their separation from one another is an important problem in analytical chemistry. Various attempts have been made in this line, but none of the methods appear to be quantitative.

The best known complex salt at present in use for the estimation of caesium is the compound $4CsCl, 4SbCl_5, FeCl_3$, (Godefroy, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 374; Strecker and Diaz, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1925, 67, 321; Moser and Ritschel, *ibid.*, 1927, 70, 184) the method being quantitative only under conditions which cause appreciable co-precipitation of rubidium. Various organic acids have been tried but with little success.

O'Leary and Papish (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1934, 6, 107) developed an improved method for the quantitative determination and separation of potassium, rubidium and caesium based on the use in succession of *o*-phosphomolybdic acid, silicotungstic acid and chloroplatinic acid. They observed that rubidium and caesium salts of the first named acid are insoluble, potassium salt being perfectly soluble. The caesium salt of silicotungstic acid is insoluble in 6*N* hydrochloric acid, rubidium salt being soluble. According to the authors "the method proposed does not afford the clean cut sharpness of separation that is desirable though it is much more reliable than those hitherto proposed. The average error introduced in course of the analysis by this method is 2%."

Sarkar and Goswami (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 608) while preparing the triple nitrites of the rare-earths of the series $Cs_2NaR(NO_2)_6$ (where R=Ce, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd) observed that these nitrites furnish a delicate microchemical test for caesium, the limit of identification being 4×10^{-8} g. (0.04γ). The test appears to be specific for caesium; rubidium and potassium do not interfere. It appears to be more sensitive than the triple caesium-silver-gold chloride test advocated by Emich (*Monatsh.*, 1918, 39, 775).

It has been observed by the present author that caesium is quantitatively precipitated as $Cs_2NaLa(NO_2)_6$ from its solution and that the filtrates from such precipitations always yield a negative reaction with perchloric acid, and a method has been developed for the quantitative determination of caesium and its separation from rubidium and potassium in one operation. The precipitate can be directly weighed in a gooch crucible. The compound contains 37.77% of Cs. The metal can also be determined volumetrically by estimating the nitrite content of the compound with ceric sulphate. It has been observed that even 3 mg. of caesium can be estimated accurately. The accuracy of the method has been found to be $\pm 0.2\%$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the reagent.—For reagent, a solution of sodium-lanthanum nitrite is used. A 50% solution of lanthanum nitrate was added to an equal volume of a 50%

solution of sodium nitrite. The solution was then filtered and preserved in a well-stoppered bottle. The solution should be filtered before use if found turbid due to slight decomposition with formation of basic salts.

Preparation of the standard solutions of the Alkali Salts: Potassium, Rubidium and Caesium.—The alkali salts were taken in the form of their nitrates. Rubidium and caesium nitrates were from Kahibaum & Co., and potassium nitrate, from Merck & Co., U.S.A. The spectrum of rubidium salt was found to be free from any caesium line when viewed through a direct vision spectroscope and *vice-versa*.

All solutions were made from conductivity water and standardised by the perchloric acid method after being converted into chloride by repeated evaporation with concentrated hydrochloric acid.

Solubility of the compound in Different Solvents.—The compound being moderately soluble in cold water, could not be washed with it. Even in 80% aqueous acetone, the compound was appreciably soluble, whereas sodium nitrite, the impurity to be removed, was practically insoluble in this solvent. Ethyl alcohol also behaved very similarly but the compound was found to be practically insoluble in methyl alcohol and in this solvent, sodium nitrite was known to be soluble to the extent of 4%.

Methyl alcohol was therefore used in the following experiments as wash-liquid after removing the mother-liquor with the help of a few drops of cold saturated solution of sodium nitrite.

Estimation of Caesium.—The solution was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and redissolved in the least quantity of water. It was then cooled in ice and 3 to 5 c.c. of the reagent depending on the amount of caesium taken, were then added with stirring. The solution was allowed to stand for sometime, then filtered in a weighed gooch crucible, washed first with a few drops of cold saturated solution of sodium nitrite then with ice-cold methyl alcohol and finally with ether. The crucible was then dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid and the caesium weighed as $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaLa}(\text{NO}_2)_4$ ($\text{Cs} = 37.77\%$). The results are given in Table I.

Estimation of Caesium in presence of Rubidium.—The method is identical with the one described. The rubidium was estimated in the filtrate as perchlorate after separation of lanthanum by double precipitation with ammonia and removal of ammonium salts by ignition. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE I		TABLE II			
Cs taken.	Cs found.	Cs taken.	Rb taken.	Cs found.	Rb found.
0.05158 g.	0.05165	0.05158 g.	0.04658 g.	0.05154 g.	0.04658 g.
0.02579	0.02583	0.02579	0.05823	0.02575	0.05823
0.00516	0.00514	0.01032	0.05237	0.01034	0.05236
0.02579	0.02575	0.00259	0.02612	0.00261	0.02614
0.03868	0.03864	0.01032	0.2429	0.01034	0.2428

The method worked excellently for mixtures containing rubidium chloride up to 25 times the amount of caesium chloride present. With more rubidium, results were rather high due to co-precipitation of the corresponding rubidium compound.

Estimation of Caesium in presence of Potassium.—The procedure was identical with the previous one. Potassium was estimated in the filtrate as perchlorate after the usual separation of the rare-earth. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Cs taken.	K taken.	Cs found.	K found.
0'05158 g.	0'05068 g.	0'05158 g.	0'05066 g.
0'01032	0'10136	0'01034	0'10136
0'01032	0'2506	0'01030	0'2507
0'00258	0'1267	0'00257	0'12625
0'00516	0'5068	0'00519	0'50683

TABLE IV

Cs taken.	Cs found.
0'05158 g.	0'05160 g.
0'02579	0'02582
0'01032	0'01036
0'02579	0'02573

The corresponding potassium compound $K_2NaLa(NO_2)_6$ was highly soluble in water and the method worked satisfactorily for mixtures containing potassium up to 100 times the amount of caesium present.

Volumetric determination of Caesium.—As pointed out, caesium may be precipitated as the triple nitrite and estimated by determining the nitrite volumetrically with ceric sulphate.

The method for precipitating, filtering and washing was the same as with the gravimetric method. In a 400 c.c. beaker was taken a measured volume of acidified standard ceric sulphate solution diluted with five times as much water. The precipitate along with the gooch was placed in the beaker under solution and stirred till the precipitate dissolved completely. The excess of ceric sulphate was then titrated with standard ferrous sulphate solution using ferroin (*o*-phenanthroline-ferrous complex) as an internal indicator (1 c.c. of 0'1N $Ce(SO_4)_2 = 0'002216$ g. of Cs). (Table IV)

Interfering Ions.—Anions like oxalate, phosphate, fluoride, etc., which form insoluble salts with rare-earth must be absent. Since bivalent cations like Cu, Co, Ni form some insoluble complex nitrites containing rare-earths (*cf.* Cuttica and Gallo, *Gazzetta*, 1923, 83, 374) all these ions must be absent.

Micro-estimation.

The same solutions of the alkali salts and the reagent that were used in the macro-determinations, have been used here. Standard solutions were measured out from a micro-burette. All solutions and wash liquids were prepared from conductivity water.

Estimation of Caesium.—The solution was taken in a micro-beaker kept in another small beaker, evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the residue redissolved in the least quantity of water. It was then cooled in ice and 0'5 to 1'5 c.c. of the reagent, depending upon the amount of caesium taken, was added, one drop at a time, gently rotating the beaker by the hand after the addition of each drop of the reagent. The precipitate was allowed to settle and collected on one side of the beaker. The supernatant liquid was then drawn off through Emich's asbestos packed filter-stick, and the precipitate sucked as dry as possible. Care should, however, be taken that no precipitate entered the filter stick before the filter washing was complete, as the fine precipitate often choked the filter thereby delaying filtration. It was then washed 5 to 6 times with ice-cold methyl alcohol using 0'25 to 0'5 c.c. for each washing, then once or twice with cold ether and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid, the empty beaker and the filter-stick having been dried similarly. The beaker with the precipitate and the filter-stick was then weighed in the micro-balance after taking the usual precautions of wiping with moist flannel and dry chamois respectively. Some of the results of analysis appear below in Table V.

Estimation of Caesium in presence of Rubidium.—The same procedure was followed as already described. Results of analyses are given in the table below (Table VI).

TABLE V

Cs taken.	Reagent.	Cs found.
1'289 mg.	1'0 c.c.	1'295 mg.
0'644	0'5	0'648
1'031	1'0	1'030
1'289	1'0	1'278

TABLE VI

Vol. of reagent used = 1'5 c.c.		
Cs taken.	Rb taken.	Cs found.
1'031 mg.	1'00 mg.	1'040 mg.
1'031	2'50	1'036
1'031	5'10	1'028
1'289	32'50	1'294
1'031	10'50	1'035

Estimation of Caesium in Presence of Potassium.—The procedure was the same as described in the previous cases. Table VII gives some of the results of analysis.

TABLE VII

Cs taken	K taken.	Reagent.	Cs found.
0'943 mg.	1'00 mg.	1'0 c.c.	0'952 mg.
0'943	10'00	1'5 c.c.	0'948
0'943	20'00	"	0'949
1'257	62'00	"	1'266
1'257	130'00	"	1'249

TABLE VIII

Cs taken.	Vol. (cor. for N/50 ceric sulphate).	Vol. reqd.	Cs found.
1'257 mg.	2'856 c.c.	2'837 c.c.	1'265 mg
1'289	2'922	2'909	1'295
0'943	2'145	2'129	0'950
0'043	2'122	2'129	0'040
1'031	2'327	2'373	1'028

The corresponding potassium compound $K_2NaLa(NO_2)_6$ being highly soluble in water, the method worked satisfactorily for mixtures containing potassium upto 100 times the amount of caesium present.

Volumetric estimation of Caesium.—The estimation of caesium by determining the nitrite volumetrically with ceric sulphate, was also employed successfully for the micro-estimation of the same.

The method for precipitating, filtering and washing was the same as with the gravimetric method. A known volume 3 to 4 c.c. of the standard ceric sulphate (N/50) in dilute sulphuric acid was taken from a micro-burette in the micro-beaker containing the precipitate and the filter-stick. Water (1-2 c.c.) was added to dip the stick above the constriction under solution. It was then warmed on a water-bath for a few minutes till the precipitate was completely dissolved. It was then cooled to room temperature and the excess of ceric sulphate was titrated with standard ferrous sulphate (N/50) using ferroin as an internal indicator (1 c.c. N/50 ceric sulphate = 0'443 mg. of Cs). Results are in Table VIII.

Indicator correction.—With ceric sulphate and ferroin when the standard titrating solution was sufficiently dilute, indicator correction is essential. The correction has been found to obey a linear variation and is almost exactly equal 0'2 c.c. of N/50-ceric solution for every 0'05 c.c. of ferroin added.

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